

Original Research Paper

Study on prevalence of Term Low birth weight neonates and their outcomes admitted in Government tertiary care hospital of Kanyakumari district.

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Low Birth weight is defined by the World Health Organization as weight at birth less than 2500 grams in the first hour of delivery (1). Low birth weight is a valuable indicator of maternal health, nutrition, health care delivery and poverty. Neonates with low birth weight have a >20 times greater risk of dying than neonates with birth weight more than 2500 grams (2). Low birth weight also indicates malnutrition and ill health of the mother. Low birth weight babies are at a higher risk of sepsis, respiratory distress, Hypoglycemia, Hypothermia, HIE, apnea, perinatal asphyxia, PDA, IVH, congenital anomalies and neonatal deaths. **Methods:** It is a cross-sectional observational study of all term neonates with Low birth weight born in Kanyakumari Government medical college from October 1, 2020 to October 31, 2021. The clinical features, duration of hospital stay and outcomes of these neonates was analyzed. **Results:** A total of 125 children was analyzed. Results of the study showed that the prevalence of term LBW neonates was 3.4%. Majority of mothers between age group 21-30 years (77.2%) belonging to low middle socio-economic status (41.5%) delivered LBW neonates. Mean number of AN visits was 4. 85.4% mothers consumed IFA supplements. Post-natal complications include respiratory distress (28.5%), NNH (25.2%), IUGR (24.4%), sepsis (14.6%), Asphyxia (4.1%) followed by congenital anomalies (3.3%). Term LBW neonates had a mortality of 1.6%. The mean duration of hospital stay was 4 days. **Conclusion:** Low birth weight neonates are responsible for the majority of neonatal morbidity and mortality. The mortality rate among term low birth weight babies was minimal (1.6%) in our study. Morbidity, on the other hand, was on the high side. The best way to minimize the incidence of LBW newborn is prevention by improving maternal health than treatment.

INTRODUCTION:

Low birth weight is a major public health concern in developing nations, such as India. Globally, it is estimated that annually 15–20% of all newborns are low birth weight infants. Low- and middle-income countries account for a disproportionate burden of Low-birth-weight infants. There are marked global and regional variations in LBW rates. An estimated 6% of infants are born LBW in East Asia and the Pacific, 13% in Sub-Saharan Africa, and up to 28% in South Asia (3). Up to half of all LBW infants are born in south Asia (4). Infants weighing less than 2500 grams are 20 times more likely to die than bigger babies, according to epidemiological research (5). Fetal and neonatal morbidity and mortality are also strongly connected. In India, 30-35 percent of babies are born with low birth weight and more than half of these babies are born full term (6). Studies have demonstrated that reducing the burden of low birth weight would have economic benefits both to the health system and to households (7). Reducing low birth weight contributes significantly to the Millennium Development Goal [MDG] of reducing infant mortality (8). Activities aimed at achieving the MDGs will ensure that children have a healthy start in

life by assuring that pregnant woman are healthy and well-nourished, and that pregnancy and childbirth are carried out safely (9). Low birth weight also indicates malnutrition and ill health of the mother. Although advances in perinatal and neonatal care have helped in the survival of LBW babies, they suffer from sequelae like malnutrition, recurrent infections and poor neurodevelopmental outcomes. Low birth weight babies are at a higher risk of sepsis, respiratory distress, Hypoglycemia, Hypothermia, HIE, apnea, perinatal asphyxia, PDA, IVH, congenital anomalies and neonatal deaths. An understanding of the prevalence and outcomes of term low birth weight neonates can help to reduce neonatal mortality and attain the Millennium development goals. With this background, the present study is conducted to know the prevalence of low birth weight among term babies and to find out their outcomes in post-natal period.

Objectives:

To Study the prevalence of term low birth weight neonates admitted and treated in a government tertiary care hospital in Kanyakumari district To study the outcome of term low birth weight neonates admitted and treated in a government tertiary care hospital in Kanyakumari district.

Preliminary case definition

Low Birth weight (LBW) is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as weight at birth less than 2500 grams in the first hour of delivery (1). Term baby are those neonates born after 37 completed weeks up to 42 completed weeks of gestation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Study design: This is a hospital-based Cross-sectional observational study.

Study Place: Sick new-born care unit (SNCU) of Paediatric ward, Kanyakumari Government Medical College Hospital.

Study population: All term neonates with low birth weight born in tertiary hospital of Kanyakumari district who satisfied the inclusion criteria during the study period were included in this study.

Study Period: Study was conducted from 1st October 2020 to 31st October 2021.

Sample size and sample technique: 125 term Low birth weight neonates based on consecutive sampling technique was included in this study.

Inclusion criteria:

Birth weight less than 2500 grams

Gestational age of the mother is 37 to 42 completed weeks

Parents have given written consent

Exclusion criteria:

Birth weight more than 2500 grams

Birth weight less than 1000 grams

Figure 1: Prevalence of Term low birth weight in study population.

The prevalence of term low birth weight neonates was more in mothers with age between 21-30 years (77.2%) as seen in figure 1.

Figure 2: Gender distribution of Term low birth weight in study population.

Parents have not given written consent

Data collection technique and tools:

This is a hospital-based cross-sectional study conducted in Kanyakumari Government medical college hospital, Asaripallam, Tamilnadu. All of the newborns were weighed within one hour of birth, and their birth weights were measured to the closest ten grams using a baby weighing scale. Diagnosis of various disease was done on basis of clinical presentation and affordable laboratory investigations. The criteria and definition of neonatal morbidities were based upon recommendations of the National Neonatology Forum (NNF) of India. Data about socio-demographic profile of the mother, obstetric history of the mother especially about previous births, abortions, antenatal services obtained by the mother including antenatal visits, Iron and Folic acid prophylaxis was obtained. The low-birth-weight newborn was observed immediately after birth till discharge and all the minute details on mortality and morbidity of the study population was documented and analyzed.

Statistical analysis: The data was entered in Microsoft Excel 2019 and analyzed in SPSS software version 20.0. For analysis, descriptive statistics used were percentage, mean, and standard deviation (SD).

RESULTS:

A total of 125 children was studied during the study period of 12 months. Results of the study showed that the prevalence of term LBW neonates was 3.4% and mean birth weight was 1.8 grams.

The prevalence of low birth weight was equally distributed between Male and female babies as seen in figure 2.
Figure 3: Prevalence of Term low birth weight and socio-economic status.

The prevalence of term low birth weight neonates was more in mothers belonging to low middle socio-economic status (41.5%) compared to middle and high socio-economic status as seen in figure 3. Mean number of AN visits was 4 among the mothers who delivered term low birth weight neonates. In our study it was found out that 85% mothers consumed Iron and folic acid supplements during the course of pregnancy as seen in figure 4.

Figure 4: Iron and folic acid consumption among mothers.

Out of the 125 children studied, the most prevalent post-natal complications were respiratory distress (28.5%) followed by NNH (25.2%), IUGR (24.4%), sepsis (14.6%), Asphyxia (4.1%) and congenital anomalies (3.3%) as seen in figure 5.

Figure 5: Outcomes of Term low birth weight neonates.

Term LBW neonates had a mortality of 1.6% as seen in figure 6.

Figure 6: Mortality among Term low birth weight neonates.

The mean duration of hospital stay was 4 days.

DISCUSSION:

A public health strategy that focuses on better prenatal care and education is needed to reduce the prevalence of low birth weight. Interventional initiatives should be promoted in all sectors concerned with social development and social welfare schemes, not only the health sector. Women should be taught and encouraged to have regular ANC checkups, which helps identify these risk factors earlier on and improves the newborn's weight. Nair NS, Rao RP et al, conducted a community-based study in the rural regions of Udupi taluk, Karnataka state, South India, to determine the socio-demographic, maternal, and

obstetric predictors of low birth weight. Information about the families' social, demographic, and socioeconomic conditions, as well as maternal factors such as age, parity, antenatal care quality, and previous obstetric history, was collected by interviewing mothers and family members and verifying medical records through field investigators who were specifically recruited and trained for this purpose. Primi, elderly moms, and mothers who did not receive adequate antenatal care were shown to be at a higher risk (10). In a prospective hospital-based study, Raman TR, Devgan A et al, analyzed newborns to see if they had low birth weight and their risk factors. The mothers who gave birth to the most low-birth-weight

neonates were between the ages of 19 and 25. There was 48 neonates born to mothers under the age of 18 who also had low birth weight. Primiparous mothers were found to have a higher proportion of neonates with low birth weight (414/1014). There was no variability in spacing as a factor. Low birth weight newborns account for 32.7 percent of all babies born, which may be cause for concern (11).

Mondal B. et al, studied the Tangsa tribe of Arunachal Pradesh's low birth weight in relation to the baby's sex, maternal age, and parity in a hospital-based study. Low birth weight reported 28.48 percent of cases, while only 4.64 percent of neonates weighed 2000 g or less. The average birth weight was 2806 grams. Low birth weight was found to be more common in female babies than in male neonates. Parity was found to have a major impact on the occurrence of low-birth-weight babies. After the fourth parity, there was a rise in low-birth-weight newborns, and this parity also had the best outcome. Low birth weight was reported to be more common in the 5+ parity. Young mothers (those under the age of 20) had additionally (12). The prevalence and determinants of "low birth weight" among institutional deliveries were studied by Agarwal K et al. The goal of this study was to determine the epidemiological factors linked to low birth weight (LBW) among institutional deliveries in order to make appropriate recommendations to prevent LBW. In this study, 40.0 percent of mothers gave birth to babies that was underweight. The findings show that gestational age less than 37 weeks (76.5%), maternal age less than 20 years (58.5%), irregular antenatal checkup (70.5%), harsh physical work (78%), and tobacco chewing (58.5%) are all significant detriments to a healthy pregnancy (13). Bansal P et al attempted to study the prevalence of low-birth-weight newborns among institutional deliveries, as well as the relationship between socio-cultural and maternal contributing factors. Low birth weight is seen as a sensitive indicator of a country's health and development. Low birth weight newborns were found to be substantially associated with socio-cultural and maternal risk factors such as rest received in the afternoon during pregnancy, food consumption, and gestation age. The problem of low-birth-weight neonates can be reduced because most of these factors can be easily resolved by providing enough and effective antenatal care services and ensuring that they are used to their full potential (14) In our study, 28.5 percent of newborns had RDS. RDS was found in 40.6 percent of 613 newborns admitted to the neonatal critical care unit, according to Caner et al (15). The reasons for these disparities in epidemiology could be related to the participant's defined gestational age. A total of 25.2% newborns had suffered from neonatal Hyperbilirubinemia in our study in contrast to the study conducted by Manikyamba D et al where 42% of LBW babies suffered from Neonatal Hyperbilirubinemia. (16) In the present study 14.6%

term low birth weight infants had sepsis. In contrast to our study, Makhoul et al found a strong association of sepsis and low birth weight (17).

CONCLUSION:

Since ancient times, 'low birth weight babies' have been a major health concern, posing a serious threat to neonatal survival. It is commonly stated that greater the birth weight, the more developed the nation. Low birth weight neonates are responsible for the majority of neonatal morbidity and mortality. Low birth weight babies put a significant burden on the entire neonatal care service system, necessitating greater hospital stays, overall treatment, and, in general, greater resource mobilization. The mortality rate among term low birth weight babies was minimal (1.6%) in our research. Morbidity, on the other hand, was on the high side. The best way to minimize the incidence of LBW newborns and mortality is to improve maternal health. After all is said and done, it is preferable to prevent low birth weight than to treat it. However, the reality remains that reducing low birth weight is only possible by improving maternal health care services, and that aspect can only be done by improving a country's socioeconomic standard, as proven scientifically.

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